
IMPACT OF DEFICIT FINANCING ON THE GROWTH OF NIGERIA ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The research examined the impact of deficit financing on the growth of Nigeria economy from 1991 - 2023. The objectives of this study are to investigate the impact of external, and internal borrowing and tax on the Nigerian economy. Secondary data were sourced from CBN and FIRS. The research employed econometric tools of co-integration, the log-log transformation of the variables, and unit root testing aimed at determining their level of stationarity and eliminating spurious regression results. Upon this, the Vector Error Correction Model was employed to determine short and long-run interconnectivity. The error correction term (ECT) in the model shows that long-run disequilibrium is adjusted annually at a speed of 2.2%. To further ascertain this, pairwise Granger causality was carried out to show their level of direction and causality. The finding revealed that TAX has a causal effect on RGDP and external borrowing/debt (EXTD) in the short run, thereby validating Keynesian approaches. The study recommends that the government without reservation should match debt with productivity and economic objectivity. Secondly, it is only when loans are channel-fed toward productive investment and yield return that people can promptly respond to their tax obligation otherwise tax will continue to be seen as inimical by Nigerians. Moreover, the government should design tax policies that complement economic growth objectives by balancing revenue generation with minimal distortionary effects on economic activities. Finally, the country's tax base is low because of its structure and administration. The agency saddled with the collection should intensify efforts to strengthen the tax base and be decentralized to the local government level to curb the level of tax evasion and avoidance.

Keywords: Deficit financing, economic growth, domestic debt, external debt, tax, gross domestic product.

A budget deficit is a situation where the expected revenue of the government within a financial year is small/meager in relation to what it is expected to spend as its expenditure. Whenever such is experienced, a gap needs to be filled as a response to meet the constitutional responsibility of ensuring growth and development. Whenever governments experience this scenario of shortfall in revenue as against its planned expenditure, such can be funded in a variety of ways, i.e borrowing: domestic and international, increase in taxes, ordering of central bank to print money, and foreign assistance in the form grant and aid from foreign donor and agencies. However, fiscal operations through borrowing attract stringent interest on the other hand, the borrowed fund tends to rise as past deficits are added up to the current one and thus the future borrowing rate will be affected.

On the back of the foregoing, Soludo (2003) argued that countries borrow for two principal macroeconomic reasons; improvement in investment, consumption, education, health, and balance of payment deficit and when borrowing pushes beyond the international threshold, the country inevitably ends up on the wrong side of the debt laffer curve, with the result of crowding out of investment and growth, which seems to be the case of the country with historical highs of poverty. Sanusi (2003) also states that countries owe their debts to lower poverty, to better growth, and if the debt stock goes beyond a certain limit it places upon the economy a debt burden, which distorts the target objectives of monetary policy and fiscal management hence negative consequences on growth if debt is unpaid timely. Debt taken on by a nation would have positive consequences depends on the extent to which a borrowing nation can utilize the debt incurred to be put to productive or consumption assets (Ezenwa 2012).

In retrospect, the budget deficit in Nigeria dating back to 1961 is quite a justifiable one, especially after the Nigerian civil war. In 1978, the Nigeria government ran into deficit financing to the tune of \$1 billion cited in a paper Deficit Financing and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Preliminary Investigation (Akinmulegun, 2014), which enabled her to sustain the economic drive for reconstruction, rehabilitation and rebuilding of the war-ravaged economy. It has been a continuous one from the first republic till date. However, while Nigeria is not the only country that is running budget deficit financing, advanced nations also run deficit financing. Apart from the borrowing, governments of the post-independence period attempted to accelerate the pace of economic growth through different channels, one of which was the maximization of tax revenue as a means of adequately funding government-initiated programs (Ekuarhare, 1980; Ariyo, 1997). For this purpose, the global community now acknowledges that deficit finance is a fulcrum that crosses the chasm of insufficiency of the anticipated revenues. It is the creation or introduction of new money to fill up the gap between planned expenditure and estimated receipt of government. The stride for economic stability also made deficit finance necessary to support the growth and development that the country wants to realize in the long term. Keynes (1936) argued that deficit financing should be instituted at the state at which consumer spending drops particularly in the depression period and the imbalances could be restored by the deliberate introduction of fiscal deficit financing the case is not far from Nigeria in the aspect of borrowing to finance the government budget.

Domestic borrowing causes competition with private investors vying for funds for capital projects hence crowding out private investors as argued by the classicalists. On the other side deficit operation tax is collected by the governments and is used to provide for public good/common benefit for everyone, largely in the form of provision of public welfare

services. With the continuous decline of oil revenue as a result of the recession and global oil glut, the government has been driven to maximize measures in her strategy/approach to expand her tax base through agencies like Federal Inland Revenue which has achieved tax revenue of ₦5.260, ₦4.952, 6.405 Trillion Naira in 2019, 2020 and 2021 respectively as indicated in Federal Inland Revenue tax report.

However, the intrigues show that government expenditures in the last four decades have consistently embarked on budget deficit financing to fill the gap due to the rise in the population, insecurity, and dynamics in the business cycle yet the desired level of projection has not been achieved despite the dynamism trend in borrowing, series of tax reform that got crash because of improper tax administrative mechanism intended to increase Corporate, Petroleum, and Education, Value Added Tax which in recent time aim to boost tax revenue base. It is upon this backdrop of effort that this study raises questions and hypotheses to say that the fiscal deficit operation of government which includes external and internal borrowing and taxation has not positively impacted the economy of Nigeria in the last three decades ranging from 1991-2023.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical framework

Theoretical framework of this study is based on the John Maynard Keynes (1936) which states that government spending increase public demand and boost economic growth. By and large consumer is the main driving force in an economy; effort should be consistently made to support their demand through expansionary fiscal policy. A well justifiable expansionary fiscal policy like deficit financing is meant to fill in the infrastructural deficit, increases country capital accumulation, reduces the level of unemployment and at the long run ensuring a sustainable growth amidst consequences of inflation and interest rate hike.

2.2 Empirical Literatures Review

No country is an island, and thus they do evolve and relate to each other in terms of economic and social benefit. Oloyede (2002) proposed that dual-gap analysis provides an improved basis for showing that a country's growth is a function of investment, and that investment that necessitates domestic savings is not enough to guarantee growth. External borrowing has become a very popular financing method in many developing countries in that, in most developing countries, domestic capital markets are too small, and domestic borrowing opportunities are very limited, governments borrow from external sources to finance deficit (Harris, 1988). Poor external debt management creates a burden on the borrowing nation and this could be a disincentive to domestic enterprise since a disproportionate fraction of national earnings would be channelled to debt service payments thereby stifling economic growth.

Most the time without looking outward, governments usually issue bonds to match or leverage their deficits. They can be purchased by the Central Bank of that country using open market injections. Debt issuance will lead to raised notches in Public debt, private sector net worth, debt service (interest payments), and interest rate. Deficit spending may however be consistent with public debt to remain stable as a proportion of GDP, depending on the level of GDP growth (Baumol and Alan, 2005).

This study is deeply rooted in Keynes John Maynard Keynes's economic growth theory (1936) which is supported by (Ali, 2014; Bakare et al., 2014; Muhammad et al., 2014; Okelo et al., 2013; Okoro, 2013; Ojong and Hycenth, 2013) in their research. According to

Keynesian theory, public spending can be a force for economic expansion by increasing government consumption expenditure, in which an increase in government consumption expenditure leads to an increase in employment, profits, and investments. The model gives high priority to the fact that during an economic crisis, the government can reverse those economic problems, arising from low demand by taking money from the private sector and giving it back to the private sector through different expenditures.

Ejike (2022) empirically conducted research on the implications of public sector budget deficit financing on economic growth in Nigeria from 2003-2018. The study aimed to determine the best financial alternative for deficit financing. The studied variables are bank credit for government, non-bank public credit, average and mean, and external loan. The result indicates bank credit and non-bank public to growth rate proportion, which way and means are inversely proportion to GDP. The outcome also shows that external financing shows a negative or inverse relationship with GDP. Okachukwu, Kenechukwu, and Amalachukwu (2019) also investigated deficit financing and economic growth in Nigeria between the years 1987 - 2017 by applying the economic tool of the VAR model. Study variables are domestic borrowing, external reserves, debt servicing, foreign borrowing, and private consumption expenditure. The discovery shows deficit financing has a positive, but not statistically significant association with economic growth, and it is therefore proposed that the government of a country should broaden the revenue base and implement fiscal and monetary control. Monogbe and Okah (2017) conducted an empirical study involving deficit financing "Deficit financing in the process" of Economic Development in Nigeria" from 1981-2015 by using ECT and the Granger causality test. The explanatory variables in the course of research are domestic debt, human development index (HDI), and budget deficit (BD). Discovery revealed that for every 1% rise in foreign debt 0.00003% more GDP is stimulated, which is quite small, but not for, domestic debt. Igbodika, Jessie, and Andabai (2016) examined the correlation between domestic debt and economic growth performance in the Nigerian economy, 1987–2014, and applied the econometric methods of OLS to this study. The variables taken to analyze were gross domestic product (as an indicator for economic growth), domestic debt, interest rate, and inflation rate. The result showed that interest rate has an inverse significant effect on the gross domestic product in Nigeria. Also, Domestic debt impacts positively on GDP. Pattillo, Helene, and Luca (2004) investigated the effect of external borrowing on economic growth. This paper considered 61 developing countries during the time frame of 1996-1998. The outcome indicated that external borrowing hurts economic growth, as it decreases the ratio of exports, and 35-40 debt-to-GDP is not satisfactory for economic growth.

3.METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design: This study employed a causal-comparative or ex-post facto research design. It is a quantitative framework in which investigation of an economic problem commences after the experience or event has occurred without researcher interferences on the data. The Experimental/Ex-post facto or casual comparative is important for this study because it will analyze time series and their characteristics and how the variables exogenous affect or influence the endogenous variables

3.2 Model Specification: Vector Error Correction Mechanism was used for the research. It's a system of research equations that takes into consideration of variables as endogenous and resolved simultaneously. The criterion for the model is that the variables must be stationary at first difference and co-integrated. The specifications of these models are shown below.

$$\text{Real GDP Equation: } D(\text{LGDP}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{lnrgdp}(\text{LRGDP}(-1) - \text{LEXTD}(-1) + \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - \text{LTAX}(-1) + \text{ln}\beta_2 \text{gdp}(\text{LGDP}(-1)) + \beta_3 \text{lnextd}(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + \beta_4 \text{lnmdmdebt}(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + \beta_5 \text{Intax}(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C_{16} \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

$$\text{External Debt Equation: } D(\text{LEXTD}) = \beta_0 + \beta_7 \text{lnextd}(\text{LRGDP}(-1) - \text{LEXTD}(-1) + \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - \text{LTAX}(-1) + \beta_8 \text{lnrgdp}(\text{LGDP}(-1)) + \beta_9 \text{lnextd}(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + \beta_{10} \text{lnmdmdebt}(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + \beta_{11} \text{Intax}(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C_{12} \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

$$\text{Domestic Debt Equation: } D(\text{LDMDEBT}) = \beta_{13} \text{lnmdmdebt}(\text{LGDP}(-1) - \text{LEXTD}(-1) - \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - \text{LTAX}(-1) + \beta_{14} \text{lnrgdp}(\text{LGDP}(-1)) + \beta_{15} \text{lnextd}(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + \beta_{16} \text{lnmdmdebt}(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + \beta_{17} \text{Intax}(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C_{18} \dots \dots \dots (3.3)$$

$$\text{Tax Equation: } D(\text{LTAX}) = \beta_{19} \text{lnrgdp}(\text{LRGDP}(-1) - \text{LEXTD}(-1) + \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - \text{LTAX}(-1) + \beta_{20} \text{lnrgdp}(\text{LGDP}(-1)) + \beta_{21} \text{lnextd}(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + \beta_{22} \text{lnmdmdebt}(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + \beta_{23} \text{Intax}(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C_{24} \dots \dots \dots (3.4)$$

Where:

LRGDP = Log of real gross domestic product

LEXTD = Log of external borrowing/debt,

LDMDEBT = Log of Domestic borrowing/debt and

LTAX = Log of Tax revenue

These variables are treated as dependent variables with one difference lag.

The term β_0 is the constant of regression;

$\beta_1 - \beta_{24}$ are the associated endogenous variable's coefficients whilst

U_t is the error term.

The a priori expectation of the variables in the model is expected to be positive within alpha 10% level of significance considering the VECM and impact of deficit financing on the economy.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1: Unit Root Test Analysis

Variables	T.Statistics	10% Abs value	Prob @ 10%	Remark	Difference
Lrgdp	-3.0728834	-2.619160	0.0392	Reject the null	I(1)
Lextd	-6.293652	-2.619160	0.0000	Reject the null	I(1)
Lgdomd	-5.280409	-2.619160	0.0000	Reject the null	I(1)
Ltax	-6.8342514	-2.619160	0.0000	Reject the null	I(1)

Source: Author's E-view computation

For LRGDP, comparing the critical T-value against the test statistics, findings indicate that at 10% the absolute value of the critical value is **-2.619160** while that of the test statistic is **-3.0728834** which indicates that the critical value is less than the T. Statistics therefore I can say that RGDP has no unit root. The probability value is **0.0392**. ForEXT, comparing the critical value against the test statistics findings indicate that at 10% the absolute value of the critical value is **-2.619160** while that of the T. Statistic is **-6.293652** which indicates that the critical value is less than the test statistics therefore EXT has no unit root with a probability value of **0.0000**. Also, for DOMDEBT at 10% critical value is **-2.619160** while that of the test statistic which indicates that the critical value is **5.280409** in absolute terms is less than the T. Statistics therefore I can say that DMDEBT has no unit root with a probability of **0.0001**. Finally, Also, for TAX at 10% critical value is **-2.619160** while that of the T.

Statistics is which indicates that the critical value is - **6.832514** in absolute terms less than the T. Statistics therefore TAX has no unit root with a probability value of **0.0000**.

4.2: Co-integration Test Result

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.1 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.631714	66.70898	44.49359	0.0003
At most 1 *	0.520756	35.74324	27.06695	0.0092
At most 2	0.340479	12.94130	13.42878	0.1170
At most 3	0.001219	0.037806	2.705545	0.8458

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.1 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.1 level

In the Johansen Co-integration above, the hypothesized numbers of the equation are stated as Null. The Trace test shows that two null hypotheses with asterisk signs are rejected. None and at most 1 of the hypotheses equations are rejected with a probability value less than 10% viz-viz 0.0003 and 0.0092 respectively. It tells or informs that there is a co-integration among the variables. At most 2 and 3 null hypotheses cannot be rejected because the probability value of 0.1170 and 0.8485 each exceed the value of 10% of significance

4.3.: Model Estimation Results

Vector Error Correction Model Result and Analysis

CointegratingEq:	CointEq1			
LRGDP(-1)	1.000000			
LEXTD(-1)	-0.406294 (0.17830) [-2.27868]			
LDMDEBT(-1)	1.294951 (0.44422) [2.91509]			
LTAX(-1)	-1.420924 (0.37591) [-3.77995]			
C	-0.784918			
Error Correction:	D(LRGDP)	D(LEXTD)	D(LDMDEBT)	D(LTAX)
CointEq1	-0.021570 (0.01260) [-1.71207]	0.611842 (0.26202) [2.33506]	0.016777 (0.07270) [0.23076]	0.161789 (0.10788) [1.49967]
D(LRGDP(-1))	0.430558 (0.16982) [2.53534]	0.449565 (3.53190) [0.12729]	-0.350582 (0.97999) [-0.35774]	1.774528 (1.45418) [1.22029]
D(LEXTD(-1))	-0.000683	-0.215933	0.021314	0.153506

	(0.00886)	(0.18423)	(0.05112)	(0.07585)
	[-0.07712]	[-1.17212]	[0.41697]	[2.02379]
D(LDMDEBT(-1))	-0.003042	-0.312499	-0.001136	-0.079151
	(0.03662)	(0.76167)	(0.21134)	(0.31360)
	[-0.08307]	[-0.41028]	[-0.00537]	[-0.25239]
D(LTAX(-1))	-0.037786	0.096068	0.124902	0.106036
	(0.02079)	(0.43248)	(0.12000)	(0.17806)
	[-1.81710]	[0.22213]	[1.04086]	[0.59549]
C	0.033829	0.187418	0.178311	0.082095
	(0.01330)	(0.27651)	(0.07672)	(0.11385)
	[2.54442]	[0.67779]	[2.32407]	[0.72109]
R-squared	0.375387	0.237315	0.052400	0.216502
Adj. R-squared	0.250464	0.084778	-0.137121	0.059802
Sum sq. resids	0.029170	12.61721	0.971378	2.138868
S.E. equation	0.034159	0.710414	0.197117	0.292497
F-statistic	3.004954	1.555786	0.276485	1.381637
Log likelihood	64.02615	-30.05375	9.689827	-2.544580
Akaike AIC	-3.743623	2.326048	-0.238053	0.551263
Schwarz SC	-3.466077	2.603594	0.039493	0.828809
Mean dependent	0.048067	0.136027	0.184605	0.193643
S.D. dependent	0.039455	0.742589	0.184851	0.301656
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		1.45E-06		
Determinant resid covariance		6.14E-07		
Log likelihood		45.76100		
Akaike information criterion		-1.145871		
Schwarz criterion		0.149343		

Source: Author's E-view

4.4 P-Value of the Regressors

This aspect forms the basis of the research analysis as it showcases the entire system equation and the probability level of each of the regressors. In the previous model estimate above the P-value is not indicated and it is the p-value that gives statistical relevance to either the coefficient or t-statistic in a series. With e-view software package revealed the relevance of the regressors through the p-value and it is shown in the table below.

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	-0.021570	0.012599	-1.712072	0.0900
C(2)	0.430558	0.169823	2.535337	0.0128
C(3)	-0.000683	0.008858	-0.077125	0.9387
C(4)	-0.003042	0.036623	-0.083068	0.9340
C(5)	-0.037786	0.020795	-1.817097	0.0722
C(6)	0.033829	0.013295	2.544416	0.0125
C(7)	0.611842	0.262024	2.335056	0.0215
C(8)	0.449565	3.531896	0.127287	0.8990
C(9)	-0.215933	0.184225	-1.172115	0.2439
C(10)	-0.312499	0.761673	-0.410280	0.6825
C(11)	0.096068	0.432481	0.222132	0.8247
C(12)	0.187418	0.276514	0.677787	0.4995
C(13)	0.016777	0.072703	0.230759	0.8180
C(14)	-0.350582	0.979987	-0.357742	0.7213

C(15)	0.021314	0.051117	0.416975	0.6776
C(16)	-0.001136	0.211340	-0.005374	0.9957
C(17)	0.124902	0.120000	1.040856	0.3005
C(18)	0.178311	0.076724	2.324071	0.0221
C(19)	0.161789	0.107883	1.499675	0.1368
C(20)	1.774528	1.454180	1.220294	0.2252
C(21)	0.153506	0.075851	2.023791	0.0457
C(22)	-0.079151	0.313602	-0.252393	0.8013
C(23)	0.106036	0.178065	0.595493	0.5529
C(24)	0.082095	0.113848	0.721086	0.4725

Determinant residual covariance 6.14E-07

$$\text{Equation: } D(\text{LRGDP}) = C(1) * (\text{LRGDP}(-1) - 0.4062942125 * \text{LEXTD}(-1) + 1.29495053457 * \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - 1.42092421892 * \text{LTAX}(-1) - 0.784918237096) + C(2) * D(\text{LRGDP}(-1)) + C(3) * D(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + C(4) * D(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + C(5) * D(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C(6)$$

Observations: 31

R-squared	0.375387	Mean dependent var	0.048067
Adjusted R-squared	0.250464	S.D. dependent var	0.039455
S.E. of regression	0.034159	Sum squared resid	0.029170
Durbin-Watson stat	2.184751		

$$\text{Equation: } D(\text{LEXTD}) = C(7) * (\text{LRGDP}(-1) - 0.4062942125 * \text{LEXTD}(-1) + 1.29495053457 * \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - 1.42092421892 * \text{LTAX}(-1) - 0.784918237096) + C(8) * D(\text{LRGDP}(-1)) + C(9) * D(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + C(10) * D(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + C(11) * D(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C(12)$$

Observations: 31

R-squared	0.237315	Mean dependent var	0.136027
Adjusted R-squared	0.084778	S.D. dependent var	0.742589
S.E. of regression	0.710414	Sum squared resid	12.61721
Durbin-Watson stat	2.028913		

$$\text{Equation: } D(\text{LDMDEBT}) = C(13) * (\text{LRGDP}(-1) - 0.4062942125 * \text{LEXTD}(-1) + 1.29495053457 * \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - 1.42092421892 * \text{LTAX}(-1) - 0.784918237096) + C(14) * D(\text{LRGDP}(-1)) + C(15) * D(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + C(16) * D(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + C(17) * D(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C(18)$$

Observations: 31

R-squared	0.052400	Mean dependent var	0.184605
Adjusted R-squared	-0.137121	S.D. dependent var	0.184851
S.E. of regression	0.197117	Sum squared resid	0.971378
Durbin-Watson stat	1.900455		

$$\text{Equation: } D(\text{LTAX}) = C(19) * (\text{LRGDP}(-1) - 0.4062942125 * \text{LEXTD}(-1) + 1.29495053457 * \text{LDMDEBT}(-1) - 1.42092421892 * \text{LTAX}(-1) - 0.784918237096) + C(20) * D(\text{LRGDP}(-1)) + C(21) * D(\text{LEXTD}(-1)) + C(22) * D(\text{LDMDEBT}(-1)) + C(23) * D(\text{LTAX}(-1)) + C(24)$$

Observations: 31

R-squared	0.216502	Mean dependent var	0.193643
Adjusted R-squared	0.059802	S.D. dependent var	0.301656
S.E. of regression	0.292497	Sum squared resid	2.138868
Durbin-Watson stat	2.146292		

Source: Author E-view computation

E-view assigned numbering to each coefficient in each equation with p–p-value specified; LRGDP, LEXTD, LDMDEBT, and LTAX respectively. From the numbering, the p-value attached to the significance of each coefficient and the one that is not. The long run coefficient is expected to show a negative coefficient of -0.021570 detailing more on the

relevance of ECT of the system equation. The corresponding P-value of the long- run error correction term in (C1) corresponding to the Gross Domestic Product coefficient is -0.021570 revealing that it is self-adjusting toward equilibrium and significant because the P-value is lower than the 10% level of significance. In the case of (C7) which represents the External debt long run ECT shows a positive coefficient of 0.611843 with a significant probability of 0.0215. This tells that there is no long-run convergence because the ECT is supposed to be negative and significant. Similarly, the (C13) coefficient is 0.096068 with a probability value of 0.8249 > 10 % level of significance. Finally, the (C19) ECT long run coefficient of 0.161789 with a p-value of 0.1368 is higher than 10%. In conclusion, the long-run causal effect shows on only LRGDP Equation (C1).

However, the short-run causal effect of the system equation for the LRGDP equation will be the coefficient of (C3) (C4), and (C5). In this case only (C5) that is LTAX is significant in explaining the short causal relationship with LRGDP because the p-value is well lower than 10%. The short-run for the LEXTD equation will be (C9), (C10), and (C11). Their respective p-value is higher than 10% thus not significant. In the case of the LDMDEBT short-run system equation, there will be coefficients (C15), (C16), and (C17). None seem to be significant at 0.10% in the table. Finally, in the LTAX short-run equation, one will be looking at coefficients (C21), (22), and (C23). Only (C21); that is LEXTD shows a statistical relevance with LTAX in the short run. (C22) and (23) don't have a relationship with LTAX.

4.5 Granger Causality Test Result

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LEXTD does not Granger Cause LGDP	31	0.68372	0.5136
LRGDP does not Granger Cause LEXTD		0.76149	0.4771
LDMDEBT does not Granger Cause LRGDP	31	1.13725	0.3361
LRGDP does not Granger Cause LDMDEBT		1.94751	0.1629
LTAX does not Granger Cause LRGDP	31	3.01499	0.0664
LRGDP does not Granger Cause LTAX		0.77035	0.4731
LDMDEBT does not Granger Cause LEXTD	31	1.26868	0.2980
LEXTD does not Granger Cause LDMDEBT		0.69959	0.5059
LTAX does not Granger Cause LEXTD	31	0.65968	0.5255
LEXTD does not Granger Cause LTAX		2.13378	0.1387
LTAX does not Granger Cause LDMDEBT	31	1.34436	0.2782
LDMDEBT does not Granger Cause LTAX		0.96967	0.3925

From the table, the direction of the causal effect using decision criteria such that when the P-value < 0.10% level of significance the null hypothesis is rejected thus; For the EXTD & GDP relationship, the hypotheses that EXTD fails to grangers cause GDP can't be rejected because the probability value of F-Statistic is above 0.10 %. Also, the relationship between GDP and EXTD can't be rejected because the value is above 10 %. Overall, the directional effect is independent. For the DMDEBT & GDP relationship, the null hypotheses can't be rejected because the probability value is higher than 10%. Similarly, the GDP to DMDEBT relationship cannot be rejected because P-value is greater 10%. So, the GDP relationship with DMDEBT is independent. For the TAX & GDP relationship, it shows that the null hypothesis is rejected because P-value is lower than 10 %. But GDP relationship with TAX shows null is

truly reason to the fact that the p-value of F-statistics is lower than 0.10 %. So, the relationship is unidirectional. For DMDEBT & EXTD relationship can't be rejected because the p-value of F. statistic is higher than 10% thus an independent relationship. Also, EXTD & DMDEBT cannot be rejected because it is well above the level of significance 0.10%. For, TAX & EXTD relationship and EXTD & TAX relationship. Both cannot be rejected because the p-value TAX to EXTD, EXTD & TAX are 0.1759 & 0.1126 respectively. Indicating that both are independent. For the TAX & DMDEBT relationship, the hypothesis that Tax fails to granger cause DMDEBT can't be rejected because the p-value is higher above 10 % thus the direction is independent. While in the case of DMDEBT & TAX cannot be rejected on the grounds that the p-value of 0.1305 is higher than 0.10% level of significance.

4.2.1 VEC Residual Test Result.

i. VEC Residual Heteroskedasticity Tests:

No Cross Terms (only levels and squares)

Joint test:

Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
104.1617	100	0.3679

This table showcases VEC residual heteroskedasticity test revealing that the model estimate is homoscedasticity with a p-value of 0.3679 which is $> 0.10\%$ and it is a great relief.

ii. VEC Residual Normality Test Result:

Component	Kurtosis	Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
1	3.116008	0.017383	1	0.8951
2	7.058478	21.27536	1	0.0000
3	6.189261	13.13804	1	0.0003
4	3.773206	0.772219	1	0.3795
Joint		35.20300	4	0.0000

The VEC normality shows that the Jarque-Bera Joint test reveals that the p-value of 0.0000 is less than 0.10%. The Jarque-Bera Joint tests picture both the kurtosis and skewness together. Though, individually RGDP and Tax are normally distributed with probability levels of 0.8951 and 0.3795 respectively.

iii. VEC Residual Serial Correlation:

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob
1	6.249793	0.9852
2	7.978866	0.9495

Probs from chi-square with 16 df.

VEC residual serial correlation was tested on the VEC Model estimate using two lag, it turned out to be free from autocorrelation with two prob. values of 0.9852 & 0.9494 which are above the 10% level of significance thus showing that the model is free from serial correlation or autocorrelation.

5.1 SUMMARY OF MAJOR FINDINGS

This research work identified the relationship between disaggregated fiscal deficit financing in Nigeria. The research work answered the research questions and tested hypotheses formulated in chapter one. The study adopted an ex-post facto research methodology.

The major findings of this research are that;

- i. Error Correction Term of the GDP equation (C1) with coefficients -0.021570 is self-adjusting with a negative sign and significant p-value of 0.0900 at 10% level
- ii. The external debt (C7) coefficient of 0.611843 and a p- p-value of 0.0215 as a component of budget deficit financing do not have run casual relationship. The p-value is significant but since the coefficient is not self-adjusting or converging because the sign of the coefficient is not negative.
- iii. Domestic borrowing/debt equation (C13) coefficient of 0.016777 is insignificant in explaining economic growth long-run causal relationship since the probability value is 0.8180 and well above 10%.
- iv. Finally, the Tax equation is denoted by (C19) with a P-value of 0.1368 and is insignificant in explaining deficit financing in the long run however granger causes external debt in the short run.

5.2 Conclusion

The research work has its basis in the Keynesian theory that economic growth can be stimulated by fiscal government operation most especially when it becomes necessary to incur debts and increase tax with emphasis on Nigeria. However, our findings revealed that tax has a causal relationship with Real GDP and external borrowing, thereby validating Keynesian position. The research uses the raw data to determine whether the variables are co-integrating and the result of Johansen revealed two co-integrated equations, the data were all logged to determine their order and level of stationarity and found to be in order one which prompted the usage of VECM to ascertain the long run and short run causal effect.

Borrowing from whatever sources can become detrimental and a great burden if it is not directed to an investment or project that can yield constant return to repay as when due and increase GDP. Caution should always be the watchdog otherwise interest on the loan borrowed can invoke a high tax on the masses and distort the inter-generational equity in short run term and in the long run which goes the saying that debt is a crime when it is not directed to meet the needs of the masses.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Judicious uses of debt depend on the political will of the government. Government should, without reservation always match every debt with the economic objective of ensuring growth and development.
- ii. Every loan taken to finance expenditure must be the type that can generate a quick return on assets so that the outstanding loan with interest can be repaid. Only when loans are channel-fed toward productive investment and yield returns that peoples can promptly respond to their tax obligation, otherwise tax will continue to be seen as inimical by Nigerians.

iii. The country's tax base is low because of its structure and administration. The agency saddled with the collection should intensify efforts to strengthen the tax base and be decentralized to the local government level to curb the level of tax evasion and avoidance.

iv. Governments should design tax policies that complement economic growth objectives by balancing revenue generation with minimal distortionary effects on economic activities

v. Tax revenues should be efficiently allocated to projects with measurable outcomes, especially those that enhance economic productivity. Transparency and accountability in the use of tax funds can boost public trust and compliance.

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